
Abstract of the Project¹ from OHBM Brainhack (Hackathon 2018)

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Title: Anomaly detection from time-series fMRI data of schizophrenia patients.

Background and Purpose of the Project: Anomaly detection from the time-series fMRI data is an active area of research. The fMRI data comprises 3-D brain scans acquired over time. Each voxel of the 3-D brain volume contains a value denoting the signal intensity at a particular time for a particular task performed by the subject. Schizophrenia is a severe mental disorder that affects different regions of the brain, often involving hallucinations and delusions. Detecting the anomaly in temporal data and identifying the activated voxels will help to reduce the features for the diagnosis of schizophrenia. Currently, techniques like GLM and ICA are used to detect the voxel activity and to reduce the data by removing the time variable. Identification of affected regions in schizophrenia may help us understand the condition and effect of disorder better and may also assist in deciding the line of treatment.

The objectives of the Project:

- 1) To find the relevant voxel having a significant change in activation.
- 2) Developing a fast and simple tool for dimension reduction.
- 3) Statistical analysis based feature selection for task-related fMRI data without giving prior information about task details.

The Plan of Work: The fMRI data of schizophrenia patients and healthy controls performing auditory oddball (AUD) task, openly available at FBIRN phase II data repository will be used in this project. Each subject's data consist of four runs of AUD task. Mean and median-based statistical methods will be applied voxel-wise on the data of each subject, identifying the relevant voxels activated across their time course. Discrete wavelet transform may be applied voxel-wise to the fMRI time-series signals to detect outliers. The detection of outliers will help us to understand the nature of the activation of the voxel, and the activated voxels may be selected as the relevant features to be fed into the classifier. The mean and median-based method may work better in terms of accuracy classifying the healthy and schizophrenia subjects when compared to features selected by the standard GLM approach. To implement the project, tools like Matlab or Python will be used for coding, SPM8 will be used for GLM, and MriCro/ MANGO for visualization of the brain image.

The benefit to the Community: To the best of our knowledge, till date, there is no study performed on time-series fMRI data involving schizophrenia patients for outlier detection to select activated voxels that helps in the classification task. This project will throw light on the recent research on time-series analysis of task-related fMRI data and may act as an alternative option to the standard GLM approach to convert 4-D fMRI data into a 3-D statistical parametric map volume.

¹ This project was performed at the OHBM Brainhack 2018, National University of Singapore (NUS), Singapore during June 14-16, 2018.